

Effective decision-making requires data and knowledge tailored to the needs of decision-makers to address specific challenges of Arctic communities

Recommendations

For researchers

1 Understand the Policy Landscape

Research should respond to the needs of policymakers, in a language they understand.

2 Emphasize Socio-economic Implications

Community engagement and co-creation ensures that findings are relevant and useful.

For decision-makers and researchers

3 Prioritize Long-term Collaboration

Cooperation between municipalities and regions should focus on concrete topics and actions for climate and economic transitions.

4 Develop Arctic Specific Benchmarks and Share Best Practices

Supporting progress toward sustainability in Arctic regions involves tracking how different communities are performing, identifying effective approaches, sharing successful examples and highlight areas for improvement.

5 Improve Access to Local Data

Creating a publicly available pan-Arctic database of local planning documents improves accessibility.

6 Promote Research-Municipality Partnerships

Success stories from collaboration should be highlighted and encourage funding.

Key Challenges

Policymakers face several obstacles when trying to use scientific information to guide their decisions. Although research institutions are eager to engage, complex procedures and limited resources often prevent local authorities from fully participating. To strengthen collaboration, institutions should adopt more flexible and streamlined approaches that ease these challenges and improve efficiency.

Main concerns of consulted experts regarding the scientific data.

- Lacking applicability to local conditions
- Lacking socio-economic conclusions in data reports
- Data reports are using too complicated language
- Insufficient data accessibility
- Delays in data delivery
- Insufficient awareness about existing data
- Lacking coordination of knowledge and data from different sources

Turning Data into Action

To ensure high-quality data informs decision-making, several approaches can help make research more accessible, understandable, and relevant to local needs.

- Clearly identified sources
- Comprehensive data interpretation
- Includes comparisons
- Content simplicity
- Clearly explained methodology
- Conforming with management standards

Criteria Prioritized by Decision-Makers for Enhancing Data Understandability.

Key elements to make research results more useful, based on stakeholder consultations from 2021-2025 with 53 municipal and regional administrators.

Map of governing bodies or research institutions that contributed to research

